

State of play and future directions in industrial computer vision AI standards

Artemis Stefanidou

*Dept. of Informatics and Telematics
Harokopio University of Athens
Athens, Greece
astefanidou@hua.gr*

Panagiotis Radoglou-Grammatikis

*K3Y Ltd.
Sofia, Bulgaria
pradoglou@k3y.bg*

Vasileios Argyriou

*Dept. of Networks and Digital Media
Kingston University
Kingston upon Thames, United Kingdom
vasileios.argyriou@kingston.ac.uk*

Panagiotis Sarigiannidis

*Dept. of Electrical and Computer Engineering
University of Western Macedonia
Kozani, Greece
psarigiannidis@uowm.gr*

Iraklis Varlamis

*Dept. of Informatics and Telematics
Harokopio University of Athens
Athens, Greece
varlamis@hua.gr*

Georgios Th. Papadopoulos

*Dept. of Informatics and Telematics
Harokopio University of Athens
Athens, Greece
g.th.papadopoulos@hua.gr*

Abstract—The recent tremendous advancements in the areas of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Deep Learning (DL) have also resulted into corresponding remarkable progress in the field of Computer Vision (CV), showcasing robust technological solutions in a wide range of application sectors of high industrial interest (e.g., healthcare, autonomous driving, automation, etc.). Despite the outstanding performance of CV systems in specific domains, their development and exploitation at industrial-scale necessitates, among other, the addressing of requirements related to the reliability, transparency, trustworthiness, security, safety, and robustness of the developed AI models. The latter raises the imperative need for the development of efficient, comprehensive and widely-adopted industrial standards. In this context, this study investigates the current state of play regarding the development of industrial computer vision AI standards, emphasizing on critical aspects, like model interpretability, data quality, and regulatory compliance. In particular, a systematic analysis of launched and currently developing CV standards, proposed by the main international standardization bodies (e.g. ISO/IEC, IEEE, DIN, etc.) is performed. The latter is complemented by a comprehensive discussion on the current challenges and future directions observed in this regularization endeavor.

Index Terms—Artificial intelligence, computer vision, standards, industry

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent outstanding advancements in the areas of Artificial Intelligence (AI) [1] and Machine Learning (ML) [2], largely due to the merits introduced by the so called Deep Learning (DL) [3] paradigm, have also boosted tremendous achievements in the field of Computer Vision (CV). In particular, DL methodologies rely on the use of large-scale Deep Neural Network (DNN) architectures [4]. Such DNN-based have exhibited unprecedented performance in a wide set of visual understanding tasks, clearly surpassing similar

hand-crafted approaches by a large margin. It needs to be highlighted though that the fundamental prerequisite for this eminent visual interpretation and reasoning capability is the availability of ever larger and sufficiently diverse training datasets [5], [6].

CV methods have received particular attention and have introduced increased potentials in a wide set of application sectors of far-reaching societal and economic impact, demonstrating efficient, robust and reliable technological solutions. Specifically, CV techniques have been successfully deployed in the following, among numerous other, industries: a) Manufacturing [7], b) Healthcare [8], [9], c) Agriculture [10], d) Automation [11], e) Transportation [12], f) Security [13], g) Education [14], h) Retail [15], i) Robotics [16], j) Sports [17], etc.

Despite the outstanding achievements and contributions of CV systems in multiple sectors, their deployment at industrial-scale has raised, apart from handling strictly algorithmic and technical obstacles, several challenges regarding aspects related to, among others, the reliability, transparency, explainability, interpretability, fairness, trustworthiness, security, safety, and robustness of the developed AI models [18], [19]. This fact inevitably raises the urgent demand for the development of efficient, comprehensive and widely-adopted relevant industrial standards. The latter need to handle and regulate all stages of the CV module development life-cycle, ranging from the collection of training data and the development of the actual software modules to aspects related to the usage, deployment, evaluation and adoption of the generated solutions.

In this paper, the current state of play regarding the development of industrial computer vision AI standards is systematically investigated, putting particular focus on examining crucial aspects, like model interpretability, data quality, and regulatory compliance. The main contributions of this study are as follows:

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101073876 (Ceasfire). This publication reflects only the authors views. The European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

- The specific steps involved in the AI standard development process and previous standards' examination works are discussed in detail.
- A thorough and systematic analysis of launched and currently developing CV standards, proposed by the main international standardization bodies (e.g. ISO/IEC, IEEE, DIN, etc.) is performed.
- A comprehensive discussion on the current challenges and future directions observed in the industrial CV standard regularization endeavor is provided.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows: Section II discusses the AI standard development process and previous standards' examination studies. Section III systematically analyzes the currently available industrial computer vision AI standards. Section IV details current challenges and future development directions. Section V concludes the paper.

II. AI STANDARD DEVELOPMENT PROCESS AND PREVIOUS WORK

Standards are crucial for ensuring consistency, interoperability, and quality control across multiple technological domains, including AI. A standard comprises a formally established guideline that outlines specifications, procedures, and/or criteria to achieve specific results. Such formalized guidelines promote reliability, safety, and compliance, while also fostering innovation by providing a structured framework for development and evaluation.

The creation of a standard typically involves multiple stakeholders, including industry leaders, regulatory bodies, researchers, and governmental organizations. This process generally consists of the following main steps [20], [21]:

- Proposal: Identification of the need for a new standard, often driven by emerging challenges or technological gaps.
- Development: Experts collaborate to draft specifications, considering best practices and technological feasibility.
- Review and consensus: Stakeholder feedback is collected and refinements are made to reach a consensus.
- Approval and publication: A governing body, such as ISO or IEEE, formally adopts/approves the proposed standard.
- Implementation and maintenance: The standard is adopted/used by organizations and is periodically updated so as to remain relevant to technological advancements.

Given the fact that AI-based systems continuously become more sophisticated and embedded across various sectors, ensuring their quality and compliance with regulatory frameworks remains a key priority. In this context, best practices from the software engineering field can be initially adapted to the case of AI system development, in order to create systems that are high-performing, transparent, explainable, and resilient. However, in order to address the ever growing complexity and sophisticated nature of AI systems, a combination of regulatory frameworks, engineering principles, and rigorous

evaluation metrics is required. The latter dictates the need for well-defined standards to ensure AI systems are not only innovative, but also trustworthy and regulation compliant.

Concerning AI-driven computer vision systems, these rely heavily on existing research and regulatory frameworks, in order to foster quality assurance. Continuously taking into account advancements in AI methodologies, along with compliance to industrial standards, is crucial component for ensuring accuracy and reliability of such systems. Oviedo et al. [22] perform a broad review of AI standards (mainly those defined by ISO/IEC) with a particular focus on software aspects, namely at the level of process and product quality, and at the level of data quality of applications integrating AI systems. Additionally, Vyas and Xu [23] investigate AI solutions in Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), showcasing how perception, sensor fusion, and deep learning contribute to precision in defect detection and automation. Moreover, Gültekin-Várkonyi [24] highlights the challenges posed by facial recognition technology, especially in relation to privacy risks and the importance of regulatory compliance. This underscores the necessity for clear technical specifications, data quality, and transparent terminology, enabling public understanding and adoption.

III. INDUSTRIAL COMPUTER VISION AI STANDARDS

The development of industrial AI standards for computer vision has received increased attention world-wide, with several key organizations contributing to the establishment of technical frameworks and guidelines. In Particular, the 'Canadian Standards Association Group' (CSA Group)¹ plays a pivotal role in developing standards for emerging technologies, including AI. In parallel, the 'Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada' (ISED)² institution coordinates efforts to establish regulatory frameworks for AI governance. Additionally, the 'Standards Council of Canada' has published the 'Canadian Data Governance Standardization Roadmap'³ that focuses on issues such as data governance, privacy protection, transparency, and reliability of AI systems. On the other hand, the US 'National Institute of Standards and Technology' (NIST)⁴ has developed the 'Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework 1.0' (AI RMF 1.0)⁵ for providing essential guidelines for managing risks associated with AI technologies, as well as 'A Plan for Global Engagement on AI Standards'⁶ to drive the development of AI-related consensus standards. Moreover, the European Commission coordinates the establishment of legal and ethical frameworks for AI, through initiatives like the 'AI Act'⁷ regulation framework. Similarly, technical standards are developed by organizations such as the 'European Committee for Standardization' (CEN)

¹Canadian Standards Association Group

²Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada

³Canadian Data Governance Standardization Roadmap

⁴National Institute of Standards and Technology

⁵Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework 1.0

⁶A Plan for Global Engagement on AI Standards

⁷AI Act

TABLE I
INDUSTRIAL COMPUTER VISION AI STANDARDS

(TOPIC: ‘ACCURACY, PERFORMANCE, AND PROCESSING’ (APP), ‘SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE’ (SDA), ‘SECURITY, ROBUSTNESS, AND RISK MANAGEMENT’ (SRR), ‘DATA MANAGEMENT AND QUALITY’ (DMQ), ‘ETHICS, PRIVACY, AND FAIRNESS’ (EPF), AND ‘BIOMETRIC IDENTIFICATION AND AUTHENTICATION’ (BIA))

Standard	Organization	Domain	Year	Topic					
				APP	SDA	SRR	DMQ	EPF	BIA
ISO/IEC DIS 9868 [25]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2025	✓		✓			
ISO/IEC WD TS 24358 [26]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2025	✓		✓		✓	
ISO/IEC DIS 19795-10 [27]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2024	✓				✓	
ISO/IEC CD 29794-5.3 [28]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2024				✓		
ISO/IEC DTS 22604 [29]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2024						✓
ISO/IEC TR 24741 [30]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2024	✓	✓	✓		✓	
ISO/IEC DIS 5152 [31]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2024	✓					
ISO/IEC TR 20322 [32]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2023					✓	
ISO/IEC TR 24714-1 [33]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2023	✓	✓	✓		✓	
ISO/IEC TR 22116 [34]	ISO/IEC	Horizontal	2021	✓				✓	
ISO/TR 24291 [35]	ISO	Healthcare and medicine	2021	✓			✓		
IEEE 3110-2025 [36]	IEEE	Horizontal	2025		✓				
IEEE 3161 [37]	IEEE	Horizontal	2023	✓	✓				
IEEE 3129-2023 [38]	IEEE	Horizontal	2023			✓			
IEEE 2945-2023 [39]	IEEE	Horizontal	2023	✓	✓			✓	
P3157 [40]	IEEE	Horizontal	2022			✓			
IEEE 2671-2022 [41]	IEEE	Manufacturing	2022	✓	✓				
DIN SPEC 13266 [42]	DIN	Horizontal	2020	✓		✓	✓		
DIN SPEC 13288 [43]	DIN	Healthcare and medicine	2021	✓		✓		✓	
JT021025 [44]	CEN, CENELEC	Horizontal	2025	✓					
BS 9347:2024 [45]	BSI	Defense and security	2024					✓	

and the ‘European Telecommunications Standards Institute’ (ETSI). All the above mentioned coordinated efforts involve activities that aim to ensure the consistent, secure, and ethical development and deployment of AI computer vision technologies.

The main organizations driving the development of industrial computer vision AI standards are the ‘International Organization for Standardization’ (ISO), the ‘International Electrotechnical Commission’ (IEC), the ‘Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standards Association’ (IEEE), the ‘German Institute for Standardization’ (DIN), the ‘European Committee for Standardization’ (CEN), the ‘European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization’ (CENELEC), and the ‘British Standards Institution’ (BSI).

Table I illustrates the main industrial CV AI standards currently available, where for each record the establishing organization, the application domain, the year of publication and the particular topic that the respective standard refers to are provided. Regarding the standards’ application domain, the following main ones have been considered so far:

- **Horizontal:** This includes standards that investigate fundamental AI system properties that are tailored to multiple and diverse sectors, aiming at ensuring broad applicability, consistency, and interoperability.

ability, consistency, and interoperability.

- **Healthcare and medicine:** This comprises standards that ensure that AI technologies, such as medical imaging and diagnostic systems, meet high accuracy and safety requirements, in order to support patient health management, while complying with relevant healthcare regulations.
- **Manufacturing:** Standards under this category focus on enhancing automation, quality control, and defect detection using AI-powered vision systems, targeting to enhance reliability and efficiency.
- **Defense and security:** This incorporates standards that address privacy/ethical concerns and security risks, ensuring responsible and secure deployment of AI technologies, like facial recognition and surveillance systems.

Additionally, the available standards cover a broad range of topics, including the following main ones:

- **Accuracy, Performance, and Processing (APP):** This ensures that AI models produce reliable and consistent results, optimizing efficiency and computational requirements. It also covers performance metrics, such as precision, recall, and latency.
- **System Design and Architecture (SDA):** This focuses on

Fig. 1. Industrial computer vision AI standards

the structural organization of AI systems, including model deployment, hardware-software integration, and scalability aspects.

- **Security, Robustness, and Risk management (SRR):** This covers safeguards against adversarial attacks, system vulnerabilities, and risk mitigation strategies, in order to enhance AI reliability in critical applications.
- **Data Management and Quality (DMQ):** This focuses on data integrity, consistency, and standardization, in order to ensure high-quality training datasets and to reduce bias in AI systems.
- **Ethics, Privacy, and Fairness (EPF):** This addresses biases in AI models, user privacy protection, and adherence to ethical AI principles, in order to ensure non-discriminatory and responsible AI deployment.
- **Biometric Identification and Authentication (BIA):** This establishes protocols for secure and ethical use of facial recognition and other biometric technologies, assuring compliance with legal and privacy regulations.

Taking into account the stage within the AI system development life-cycle, CV standards can be classified in the following key categories:

- **Foundational and terminology:** These standards define fundamental principles and basic terminology, ensuring consistency and clear communication across stakeholders.
- **Measurement and test methods:** Such standards specify measurement methods and testing procedures, in order to assess reliability, accuracy, and quality aspects of AI systems.
- **Process, management, and governance:** These provide guidelines for project management, regulatory compliance, and life-cycle oversight of AI systems.
- **Product and performance requirements:** These define

specifications for functionality, safety, and performance, ensuring systems achieve expected quality levels.

- **Interface and architecture:** These outline system architecture design and integration, facilitating interoperability among components in computer vision AI systems.

The CV standards provided in Table I are classified to the above mentioned categories, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

IV. CURRENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Standardization efforts in the area of CV exhibit multiple challenges and increased potentials for future developments, stemming out from both the rapid technological advances in the field and factors like the fragmentation of standardization organizations, varying regulatory frameworks, and different ethical perspectives. Addressing these challenges will enable the establishment of more efficient and universally adopted guidelines, boosting in this way further proliferation and deployment of CV technologies. Key challenges and corresponding future directions are discussed in the followings.

A. Fragmentation of standardization bodies and regulatory frameworks

Currently, multiple (inter-)national bodies are involved in developing standards for CV, including organizations like ISO, IEEE, NIST, etc. Each such entity develops guidelines that often differ in scope and focus, leading to inconsistencies and contradictions in the produced guidelines. To make matters worse, the wide set of available (inter-)national regulatory frameworks and policies (e.g., EU AI Act, US AI governance strategies, etc.) introduce additional difficulties in achieving global convergence and consensus. In order to overcome these boundaries, closer and continuous collaboration among international organizations, governments, and private entities is needed.

B. Bias and fairness in AI/CV systems

Bias and fairness in AI remain significant concerns, as models trained on unbalanced datasets can lead to discriminatory outcomes. Although existing regulations stress the importance of bias mitigation, enforceable guidelines remain difficult to establish, due to differing ethical perspectives across different regions/states. More intense and deeper inter-national collaboration/initiatives can facilitate towards alleviating from this drawback.

C. Security and privacy in AI/CV systems

AI-based CV systems frequently process sensitive personal and industrial data, making them attractive targets for cyber-attacks, adversarial attacks, data breaches, and algorithmic manipulations. Despite the pressing need for standardized security protocols, no universally adopted solutions currently exist. Establishing globally recognized security frameworks, such as standardized encryption techniques, differential privacy methods and adversarial robustness measures, is essential to ensuring the safe deployment of AI-driven CV technologies.

D. Thorough model evaluation

Robustness and transparency in CV model evaluation is of paramount importance, as the diversity of assessment methodologies often leads to inconsistencies in performance reporting. Well-defined evaluation frameworks should be established to ensure traceability in training data, explainability of developed models and procedures, and enhancement of trust in AI-driven decision-making. Moreover, the establishment of standardized evaluation metrics and auditing mechanisms would enhance the credibility and reliability of the developed CV modules.

E. Model risk assessment

Given the rapid evolution of AI technologies, ongoing assessments are required to evaluate emerging risks. The current *build-then-test* approach in AI development often neglects long-term risks associated with fine-tuning and post-deployment adaptation. In order to address this, comprehensive risk assessment frameworks need to be established, in order to continuously evaluate/monitor AI systems throughout their life-cycle. Incorporating human oversight, leveraging safety principles from specific industries (e.g., aviation and healthcare) and adopting real-time monitoring solutions would contribute to more robust AI governance.

F. Robustness and transparency of AI/CV systems

Enhancing robustness and explainability of AI models comprises a high priority, particularly in high-risk applications, such as facial recognition and autonomous navigation. Additionally, transparency remains a pressing issue, as many AI models operate as ‘black boxes’, making it difficult to interpret their decision-making processes and to ensure accountability. Standardized testing methodologies should be implemented to assure that AI systems meet reliability and transparency requirements. Moreover, sector-specific standardization would be beneficial, since different sectors exhibit distinct operational constraints and ethical considerations.

G. Balancing with innovation potentials

CV models need to be integrated with diverse hardware and software ecosystems, while excessive standardization risks to stifle innovation. Balancing regulatory oversight with the necessary flexibility for enabling technological advancements constitutes a critical point. In this respect, a well-regulated AI/CV ecosystem would not only promote responsible innovation, but would also safeguard against potential risks associated with uncontrollable AI developments.

V. CONCLUSION

Over the last years, Computer Vision (CV) has demonstrated tremendous advances and has introduced robust technological solutions in a wide range of application sectors of high industrial interest (e.g., healthcare, autonomous driving, automation, etc.). The deployment and exploitation of CV systems at industrial-scale urgently demands, among other, the addressing of requirements related to the reliability, transparency, trustworthiness, security, safety, and robustness of the developed AI models. The latter raises the imperative need for the establishment of efficient, comprehensive and widely-adopted industrial standards. This study investigated the current state of play regarding the development of industrial computer vision AI standards, emphasizing on critical aspects, like model interpretability, data quality, and regulatory compliance. Specifically, a thorough and systematic examination of launched and currently developing CV standards, proposed by the main international standardization bodies (e.g. ISO/IEC, IEEE, DIN, etc.) was provided. In a complementary way, a comprehensive discussion on the current challenges and future development directions in the field was performed.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Wang, T. Fu, Y. Du, W. Gao, K. Huang, Z. Liu, P. Chandak, S. Liu, P. Van Katwyk, A. Deac *et al.*, “Scientific discovery in the age of artificial intelligence,” *Nature*, vol. 620, no. 7972, pp. 47–60, 2023.
- [2] I. H. Sarker, “Machine learning: Algorithms, real-world applications and research directions,” *SN computer science*, vol. 2, no. 3, p. 160, 2021.
- [3] S. Dong, P. Wang, and K. Abbas, “A survey on deep learning and its applications,” *Computer Science Review*, vol. 40, p. 100379, 2021.
- [4] J. Chai, H. Zeng, A. Li, and E. W. Ngai, “Deep learning in computer vision: A critical review of emerging techniques and application scenarios,” *Machine Learning with Applications*, vol. 6, p. 100134, 2021.
- [5] A. Shrestha and A. Mahmood, “Review of deep learning algorithms and architectures,” *IEEE access*, vol. 7, pp. 53 040–53 065, 2019.
- [6] P. Alimisis, I. Mademlis, P. Radoglou-Grammatikis, P. Sarigiannidis, and G. T. Papadopoulos, “Advances in diffusion models for image data augmentation: A review of methods, models, evaluation metrics and future research directions,” *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 1–55, 2025.
- [7] L. Zhou, L. Zhang, and N. Konz, “Computer vision techniques in manufacturing,” *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 105–117, 2022.
- [8] A. Esteva, K. Chou, S. Yeung, N. Naik, A. Madani, A. Mottaghi, Y. Liu, E. Topol, J. Dean, and R. Socher, “Deep learning-enabled medical computer vision,” *NPJ digital medicine*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 5, 2021.
- [9] S. Konstantakos, J. Cani, I. Mademlis, D. I. Chalkiadaki, Y. M. Asano, E. Gavves, and G. T. Papadopoulos, “Self-supervised visual learning in the low-data regime: a comparative evaluation,” *Neurocomputing*, vol. 620, p. 129199, 2025.
- [10] V. Dhanya, A. Subeesh, N. Kushwaha, D. K. Vishwakarma, T. N. Kumar, G. Ritika, and A. Singh, “Deep learning based computer vision approaches for smart agricultural applications,” *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, vol. 6, pp. 211–229, 2022.

- [11] G. T. Papadopoulos, M. Antona, and C. Stephanidis, "Towards open and expandable cognitive ai architectures for large-scale multi-agent human-robot collaborative learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 73 890–73 909, 2021.
- [12] G. Liu, H. Shi, A. Kiani, A. Khreishah, J. Lee, N. Ansari, C. Liu, and M. M. Yousef, "Smart traffic monitoring system using computer vision and edge computing," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 12 027–12 038, 2021.
- [13] I. Mademlis, M. Mancuso, C. Paternoster, S. Evangelatos, E. Finlay, J. Hughes, P. Radoglou-Grammatikis, P. Sarigiannidis, G. Stavropoulos, K. Votis *et al.*, "The invisible arms race: digital trends in illicit goods trafficking and ai-enabled responses," *IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society*, 2024.
- [14] S. Joshi, F. J. Agbo, and I. Jormanainen, "Towards enhancing children's science education using augmented reality and computer vision," in *2023 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–3.
- [15] M. Shoman, A. Aboah, A. Morehead, Y. Duan, A. Daud, and Y. Adu-Gyamfi, "A region-based deep learning approach to automated retail checkout," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2022, pp. 3210–3215.
- [16] G. T. Papadopoulos, A. Leonidis, M. Antona, and C. Stephanidis, "User profile-driven large-scale multi-agent learning from demonstration in federated human-robot collaborative environments," in *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*. Springer, 2022, pp. 548–563.
- [17] Y. Cui, C. Zeng, X. Zhao, Y. Yang, G. Wu, and L. Wang, "Sportsmot: A large multi-object tracking dataset in multiple sports scenes," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, 2023, pp. 9921–9931.
- [18] B. Li, P. Qi, B. Liu, S. Di, J. Liu, J. Pei, J. Yi, and B. Zhou, "Trustworthy ai: From principles to practices," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 55, no. 9, pp. 1–46, 2023.
- [19] N. Rodis, C. Sardanios, P. Radoglou-Grammatikis, P. Sarigiannidis, I. Varlamis, and G. T. Papadopoulos, "Multimodal explainable artificial intelligence: A comprehensive review of methodological advances and future research directions," *IEEE Access*, 2024.
- [20] ISO, *ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1, with ISO Supplement*, 2024.
- [21] I. SA, *IEEE standards development process*, 2022.
- [22] J. Oviedo, M. Rodriguez, A. Trenta, D. Cannas, D. Natale, and M. Piatini, "ISO/IEC quality standards for ai engineering," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 54, p. 100681, 2024.
- [23] V. Vyas and Z. Xu, "Key safety design overview in ai-driven autonomous vehicles," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.08862*, 2024.
- [24] G. Gültekin-Várkonyi, "Navigating data governance risks: Facial recognition in law enforcement under eu legislation," *Internet Policy Review*, vol. 13, no. 3, 2024.
- [25] I. D. 9868, *Information technology — Design, development, use and maintenance of biometric identification systems involving passive capture subjects*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/83613.html>
- [26] I. W. T. 24358, *Face-aware capture subsystem specifications*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/78489.html>
- [27] I. D. 19795-10, *Information technology — Biometric performance testing and reporting - Part 10: Quantifying biometric system performance variation across demographic groups*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/81223.html>
- [28] I. C. 29794-5.3, *Information technology — Biometric sample quality - Part 5: Face image data*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/81005.html>
- [29] I. D. 22604, *Information technology — Biometric recognition of subjects in motion in access-related systems*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/88840.html>
- [30] I. T. 24741:2018, *Information technology — Biometrics — Overview and application*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/80656.html>
- [31] I. D. 5152, *Information technology — Biometric performance estimation methodologies using statistical models*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/80928.html>
- [32] I. T. 20322:2023, *Information technology — Cross-jurisdictional and societal aspects of implementation of biometric technologies — Biometrics and elderly people*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/67668.html>
- [33] I. T. 24714-1, *Biometrics — Cross-jurisdictional and societal aspects of biometrics — General guidance*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/80936.html>
- [34] I. T. 22116:2021, *Information technology — A study of the differential impact of demographic factors in biometric recognition system performance*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/72604.html>
- [35] I. 24291:2021, *Health informatics — Applications of machine learning technologies in imaging and other medical applications*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/78345.html>
- [36] I. 3110-2025, *IEEE Approved Draft Standard for Computer Vision (CV) - Technical Requirements for Algorithms Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) of Deep Learning Framework*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3110/11253/>
- [37] I. 3161, *IEEE Standard for Digital Retina Systems*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3161/10879/>
- [38] I. 3129-2023, *IEEE Standard for Robustness Testing and Evaluation of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based Image Recognition Service*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3129/10747/>
- [39] I. 2945-2023, *IEEE Standard for Technical Requirements for Face Recognition*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2945/10472/>
- [40] P3157, *Recommended Practice for Vulnerability Test for Machine Learning Models for Computer Vision Applications*, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3157/10876/>
- [41] I. 2671-2022, *IEEE Standard for General Requirements of Online Detection Based on Machine Vision in Intelligent Manufacturing*, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2671/17176/>
- [42] D. S. 13266, *Guideline for the development of deep learning image recognition systems*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dinmedia.de/en/technical-rule/din-spec-13266/318439445>
- [43] D. S. 13288, *Guideline for the development of deep learning image recognition systems in medicine*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dinmedia.de/en/technical-rule/din-spec-13288/334474287>
- [44] JT021025, *Evaluation methods for accurate computer vision systems*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://aistandardshub.org/ai-standards/evaluation-methods-for-accurate-computer-vision-systems/>
- [45] B. 9347:2024, *Facial recognition technology. Ethical use and deployment in video surveillance-based systems. Code of practice*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://standardsdevelopment.bsigroup.com/projects/2022-00569#/section>